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A Comparative Study of Old and Recent Riyadh Neighborhood Forms Using Objective and Subjective Measures

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AN EXAMINATION OF RIYADH NEIGHBORHOOD FORMS USING GIS APPLICATIONS

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ملخص

تبحث هذه الورقة في خصائص تصاميم أشكال الأحياء السكنية لمدينة الرياض، والتي يمكن تصنيفها إلى صنفين إثنين بحسب الظروف التاريخية التي عرفتها المدينة. يتميز أحد هذين الصنفين بالأشكال التقليدية لأحيائه والتي تتواجد بمنطقة وسط الرياض التاريخي المعروف محلياً باسم الديرة. أما الصنف الثاني فتتميز أشكال أحيائه بخصائص التمديد العمراني وهي السمة الطاغية والغالبة على معظم الأحياء كنتيجة للتطور السريع والمنتسار لمدينة الرياض. تبنت منهجية الدراسة تصوراً تجريبياً لاستمرارية شكلية طرفها متقابلان، أحدهما أشكال أحيائه موعلة في الطبيعة التقليدية أما الطرف الآخر فهو على النقيض منه، أشكال أحيائه موعلة في الحدائق على غرار ما نجده في أحياء التمديد العمراني للضواحي. كل هذا تم بغرض إجراء عملية المقارنة والمفاضلة بين أشكال الأحياء في الرياض. كما تم الاستعانة في عملية التحليل بتطبيقات النظم التي توفرها برامج شركة إسري المتمثلة في ArcView GIS 10.1. تم اختيار أربعة مكونات كمتغيرات لقياس أشكال الأحياء وهي: كثافة استعمالات الأراضي، تمازج هذه الاستعمالات، ترابط شبكة الطرق، ومدى قابليتها للاستخدام كمسارات للمشاة. يخلص البحث في النهاية ببعض التوصيات بخصوص تصميم أشكال الأحياء السكنية للحد من التمديد العمراني الحالي وتشكيل بيئات سكنية تساعد على التعايش المشترك.

Abstract

The paper examines urban neighborhood form design attributes in Riyadh. Due to some historical Reasons, Riyadh has witnessed two types of neighborhood form development. One is characterized by traditional vernacular type, mainly in the traditional urban core (Deerah), whereas the other is portrayed as sprawling-oriented neighborhood form which constitutes the bulk of the city's recent developments. A continuum ranging from traditional type neighborhoods to sprawling ones was set up to measure and compare neighborhood attribute discrepancies and differences. Using the analysis tools provided in ArcView GIS 10.1, four sets of neighborhood components were used as measurement variables. These include land use intensity, land use mix, street network connectivity, and pedestrian accessibility. Recommendations are set forth for new neighborhood design and development to hold back the present sprawling suburbs of Riyadh. **Keywords:** Neighborhood form, New Urbanism, Riyadh, Urban Sprawl, walkability, GIS.

1. INTRODUCTION

The neighborhood is the smallest area in a city that residents can detect its configuration as a whole. Neighborhood form is therefore, an important determinant of the much broader concept of urban form. Tsai (2005) argued that urban form can be depicted from various geographical scales and classified into such levels as metropolitan area, city and neighborhood. In the literature, the issue of neighborhood form has often been discussed either in terms of urban sprawl or urban compactness (Ewing, 1997; Galster et al., 2001; Neuman, 2005).

Throughout the twentieth century, there was a preference for sprawling neighborhood forms. With the rising concerns over the sustainability of cities however, a renewed interest for compact neighborhood forms emerged. The sprawling forms were faulted for being unsustainable (Jabareen, 2006).

Riyadh neighborhood forms are no exception to such debate. Throughout most of its history, Riyadh neighborhoods have adopted relatively small compact mixed-use traditional forms. Since the mid-seventies however, they have taken on a sprawling single-use forms with automobile-dependent, split into parts and

spider-like configurations. Many scholars tend to associate low-density sprawling forms with several environmental, social, and economic problems. These problems include environmental deterioration, associated health concerns, excessive land consumption, inefficient transportation, decline of “sense of community” and loss of sense of place (Knaap, 2003).

This form of growth and development is becoming more difficult to sustain so much so that many academics and professional planners have been rallying an “anti-sprawl” movement not only to seek a cure to the ills of Riyadh development patterns, but also in search for sustainable city neighborhood forms (Choguill, 2008; Eben Salah, 2004).

2. DEFINITION OF NEIGHBORHOOD FORM

Although the concept of neighborhood as a unit of analysis has been used quite extensively for city planning and design studies, neighborhood form definition and measurement however, still linger behind. In 1929, Clarence Perry developed for the first time, the concept of “neighborhood unit” the form of which consists of a spatial residential construct with a community center and an elementary school to which families and children can walk to for their daily needs and services. Rohe (2009) argues that Perry’s neighborhood unit formula provided planners with a template to design a well-defined good neighborhood form establishing a sense of community.

If the early literature has often described neighborhood form in terms of aesthetic character and physical appearance (Sutton, 1971), there is no consensus however, among scholars on a single definition of neighborhood form. Kevin Lynch (1981) for instance, insists on the permanent physical elements such as street patterns and design, block size and form, lot configuration, public spaces and parks layout as central elements of good neighborhood form. Handy (1996) however, depicts neighborhood form as a composite of characteristics associated with land use, street network and design.

New trends of neighborhood form conceptualization seem to shy away from earlier definitions based on

physical appearance and form aesthetics to focus more on notions of walkability and sense of community. As a result, recent endeavors of neighborhood planning insist more on creating neighborhood forms that encourage walking, use of mass transit, social interaction or neighboring, and a sense of place and sense of community. The advocates of the New Urbanism approach often adopt other appellations like Traditional Neighborhood Design (TND), Transit Oriented Development (TOD), Transit Villages, Urban Villages, Pedestrian Pockets, etc.

According to New Urbanism line of thinking, the neighborhood concept is extended beyond its geographical extent to embrace a whole new set of social and economic dimensions as well as environmental and political concerns. It is clear that these new movements tend to emphasize to human contacts, group socialization and neighborliness together with a mix of uses and jobs with residences. Consequently, the neighborhood is not only a physical unit but a socio-economic unit as well (Chaskin, 2006).

In their attempt to summarize the literature on neighborhood conceptualization, Moudon et al. (2006: S102) delineate the “...neighborhood as a geographical construct of place, defined around home and everyday activities, centered on schools, community centers, parks, or retail services. Neighborhood evokes socio-physical homogeneity, a shared sense of place, connection, and access. It has multiple cognitive, economic, geographic, behavioral, cultural, and temporal dimensions”.

Neighborhood Form is therefore conceived as an assemblage of buildings, street network and blocks in an identifiable, physically bounded, and pedestrian friendly area where people can socialize, live, shop, entertain, work and perform their daily activities mainly by walking. Such definition of the neighborhood in its broadest sense encompasses both the physical structure and size of the urban fabric as well as the distribution of population within an area.

3. MEASUREMENTS OF NEIGHBORHOOD FORM

Measuring neighborhood form is still lagging behind neighborhood conceptualization. Neighborhood form measurements vary to a great extent in the literature. While some scholars solely rely on objective measures such as land use, block size, street length and width and so on to capture neighborhood form in terms of its physical structure (Herold et al., 2002; Huang et al., 2007), others include socioeconomic indicators such as population size, density, residents' demographics or other population-related characteristics (Frenkel and Ashkenazi, 2008; Kasanko et al., 2006; Tsai, 2005).

With the development of GIS technologies and the widespread use of its tools in the analysis of spatially disaggregated data, newer and more sophisticated measures of neighborhood forms have become possible. In this respect, Song and Knaap (2003) have undertaken some important studies using data at the disaggregate level to set up five dimensions to measure neighborhood form. These dimensions were street design and circulation system, density, land use mix, accessibility and walkability. Song (2005) used similar set of measures to determine how well the studied neighborhood forms were compatible with smart growth principles. In his extensive study of sustainable urban neighborhood forms, Jabareen (2006) identifies seven design concepts: compactness, sustainable transport, density, mixed land uses, diversity, passive solar design, and greening.

Relying on the capabilities offered by geographic information systems (GIS) tools, Nina Schwarz (2010) used both landscape metrics and population-related indicators to measure urban neighborhood forms in 231 European cities. In her extensive review of the literature on urban form, she summarized some 27 landscape metrics indicators and 18 socioeconomic-based indicators that were used to measure either sprawl-oriented neighborhood forms or compact ones. Schneider and Woodcock (2008) quantified sprawling neighborhood forms using size or spatial extent of sealed urban area while Huang et al. (2007) developed a compactness index and a centrality index among many other parameters like centrality, porosity and density to describe compact neighborhood forms by drawing comparisons between 77 cities worldwide.

Using GIS data computation tools, Allen (2001) developed a set of indicators called INDEX to measure urban neighborhood form. INDEX uses measures of density, nuclearity, centrality, residential proximity to retail and industrial uses, and accessibility of parks, shops, and transit. Hess and Moudon (2000) have developed measures of street connectivity as a specific feature of neighborhood form, whereas Southworth (2003) used street pattern design and livability to capture such form. Similarly, Krizek (2003) shifted the focus on the association between urban form and transportation network, while Duany (2001) developed the idea of the "transect" to describe neighborhood form.

In her attempt to review the measurement approaches of urban form, Talen (2002) identified four approaches to such measurement: the aggregate, surface, geographic and elemental approach. The aggregate approach consists of characterizing urban form as a summed or averaged aggregate measure for a particular geographic unit. Studies using census data in their representation and evaluation of urban form are an example of this approach.

The surface approach on the other hand, uses zonal representation to capture urban form. The application of cellular automata rules (Batty, 1997) and fractals (Batty, 1981), as new modeling techniques in urban form has rendered the measurement of urban morphology much more sophisticated.

The geographic approach attempts to measure the dimensions composing the physical form of the urban environment. In their influential paper Galster and his colleagues identified eight dimensions to measure urban form. These dimensions are: density, continuity, concentration, compactness, centrality, nuclearity, diversity and proximity (Galster, et. al. 2000). They asserted that differences in neighborhood urban forms depend to a great extent on the different combinations between these dimensions and the weight attached to each one. It must be pointed out that accessibility and walkability are often singled out as the most common and important measures of this category.

Finally, the elemental approach to measuring urban form focuses on the elements constituting the built

environment like buildings and the spaces surrounding them, streets, parcels and the like. Measurement variables in this approach might include number of intersections, block size, sidewalks, etc.

4. METHODOLOGY OF RIYADH NEIGHBORHOOD MEASUREMENT

The present paper sets out to examine form differences between neighborhoods in the context of Riyadh City. The term “neighborhood form” is used here to refer to all physical elements that exist within the neighborhood. That is, the buildings, streets, lots, spaces, and all other elements that make up the neighborhood form. The contention is that urban form variables such as mixed land uses, street network patterns, lot density affect the neighborhood form both as a physical and social construct through its impact on walkability and therefore social interaction and neighboring within the neighborhood.

The measurement variables were extracted from Riyadh City’s databases in geographic information systems (GIS) provided by Ar-Riyadh Development

Authority (ADA). Objective measures of neighborhood attributes included count, area, distance and ratio measures of individual and groups of destinations.

For the purpose of the present study, a quantitative method of classifying neighborhoods as either of sprawling or compact neighborhood forms is adopted. A comparison of sprawl-oriented and compact neighborhood forms is undertaken. Attributes of physical form, residential layout characteristics, indicators of street pattern, density, mixed land uses, and accessibility of each neighborhood type are then quantified and measured.

Riyadh City is subdivided into six sectors each of which is composed of a number of neighborhoods (Figure 1). The first sector however, contains a traditional core whose neighborhood forms tend to adopt a more compact configuration as opposed to more recently built neighborhoods in the remaining sectors which are usually characterized by sprawling, lower density, scattered and commercial strip development.

Figure 1: Riyadh City and its six sectors (figure to the left) as defined by Ar-Riyadh Development Authority (ADA). Sector 1 is the central area of Riyadh, Sector 2 the Northern part, Sector 3 the Eastern part, Sector 4 The Southern part, Sector 5 the Western part of the city and Sector 6 the recently annexed Der'yah area. The figure to the right highlights the traditional core in yellow (called Deerah) within the first sector which is mainly composed of older compact traditional neighborhood forms.

Figure 2: Plan (left) and Aerial view (right) of the traditional core (Deerah). (Source ADA 2005)

For measurement purposes, the values were computed for each neighborhood and then summed up for all the neighborhoods in each sector. The mean values for each neighborhood form variable were then analyzed to identify any significant differences between neighborhoods of different areas of the city. Comparisons were made between the six sectors. The traditional core area containing the old neighborhoods of the city known as *Deerah* was taken out of the first sector to be singled out as another area for comparisons (Figure 2).

For each sector, measures were calculated for four categories of neighborhood form components. These are land use intensity, land use mix, street connectivity, and pedestrian accessibility. The land use intensity component includes density measures such as population and dwelling densities, average lot

size, and the proportion of single-family dwelling units in each neighborhood area. Land use mix is captured in a ratio comparing the area of non-residential to residential uses. Two diversity measures are also implemented in which the proportions of multiple land use types are being compared. The street network design component includes a connectivity measure that considers street length per hectare, and street density. Other measures include block perimeter and block size to assess interconnectedness. Accessibility is measured through mean distances to the nearest commercial uses, schools, local mosques, neighborhood parks and primary health care services. Pedestrian access is captured by calculating the percentage of single-family housing units within 5 minutes walk of these above-mentioned amenities. The following sections present the results and findings of the study and describe how measures of the above variables were computed. The study variables are summarized in the following table.

Table 1: Table showing the study's measurement variables

categories of neighborhood form components	Measurement variables			
land use intensity	population density	dwelling density	average lot size	proportion of single-family dwelling units
street connectivity	street length per hectare	street density	block perimeter	block size
land use mix	Ratio of non-residential to residential uses		proportions of multiple land use types	
pedestrian accessibility	mean distances to commercial uses, schools, local mosques, neighborhood parks and primary health care		percentage of single-family housing units within 5 minutes walk	

5. RESULTS AND FINDINGS

The literature has developed a whole panoply of metrics to measure urban neighborhood forms. The issue of quantifying neighborhood form in this study involves the use of statistical methods to describe density, pattern and morphological features of three elements: streets, lots and building blocks.

Density measures are a well-established descriptor of either new urbanist neighborhood forms or sprawling ones. The former is characterized by compact high-density development whereas the latter is often defined as low-density scattered development. The

contention is that land use intensity is highly associated with density measures. The issue of intensity of land uses is precisely what is discussed in the following paragraphs.

5.1 Land use intensity

To capture the intensity of land use at the neighborhood level, several density measures were used. These measures include population density (persons per hectare), housing density (dwelling units per hectare) and parcel density (lots per hectare) for each neighborhood (Table 2).

Table 2: Land Use Intensity- Density measures

Density	<i>Deerah</i>	Sector 1*	Sector 2	Sector 3	Sector 4	Sector 5	Sector 6
Population Density (persons/hectare)	232.28	55.19	12.00	48.00	20.81	49.52	10
Housing Density (dwelling unit/ha)	41.06	8.15	0.45	3.48	2.04	2.55	3.85
Parcel density (Parcels/ha)	16.48	3.85	1.71	2.63	1.58	3.12	0.14

Sector 1 refers to the whole sector 1 excluding the traditional core area (Deerah).*(Source: Atlas of Riyadh Land uses, ADA: 2005).

The results indicate that older neighborhoods at the inner city (*Deerah*) tend to exhibit far higher land use intensity as measured by number of residents per hectare (232 persons/ha), housing density (41 units/ha) or even parcel density (16.48 Parcels/ha). This intensity of land uses confers to the *Deerah* neighborhoods an image of compact forms and a higher level of urban vibrancy.

However, this intensity drops sharply for the neighborhoods around the *Deerah* area as revealed by the sudden plunge of densities in sector 1 surrounding it. Population density for example has fallen by about 321% to 55.19 persons/ha. Sector 2, the northern part of Riyadh, shows a very low land use intensity as indicated by density measures of population, housing units and parcels per hectare (12, 0.45 and 1.71 respectively) (Table 1). It must be born in mind that the northern area of the city is mainly inhabited by the more affluent classes of Riyadh society who prefer to live in bigger houses built upon larger lots.

Sector 6 (*Der'yiah*) however, tends to show the least intensity of all with a population density of only 10 persons per unit area. This *Der'yiah* area used to be a small community with a traditional character at the outskirts of Riyadh. It has only recently been annexed as part of the city and labeled as sector 6. This explains why its development has been lagging far behind the mainstream city development of Riyadh.

Sectors 1, 3 and 5 seem to have more or less comparable intensities. They are mainly inhabited by families from social classes ranging from lower to upper middle socioeconomic status. Lower income families tend to populate the inner city and its vicinity in sector 4, the southern area of the city. The results seem to indicate a diminishing compactness towards the fringes of the city.

Figure 3: Plan view of the Deerah neighborhood (left) at the city core and Al-Massif quarter (right) at Sector1*. (Source ADA 2005)

5.2 Lot size

One other way to examine land use intensity is to look at the lot sizes of the two main land uses, residential and commercial, within a community. This measure is extensively used to express development density and widely promoted by new urbanists and smart growth advocates. Smaller residential and commercial lots are a proxy for higher lot density and therefore, greater land use intensity.

The data provided in Table 2 below show a mean value lot size of only 248.88 m² in Riyadh city core (Deerah). But when looking at the distribution of these lot sizes (figure a in the appendix), one can easily

notice the great majority of the values grouped around 100 m². These lot size values are the lowest in Riyadh. Sectors 1*, 2, 3,4 and 5 surrounding this core area, reveal an increase up to 218% to attain 676.88 m², 791.22 m², 741.01,742.46 and 724.54 m² respectively (Table 3).

Sector 2 in the northern part of Riyadh, an area highly cherished by families of higher socioeconomic status, has the largest average residential lot size with 791.22 m² and a standard deviation of 314.33. This indicates that the lot size distribution is grouped around the mean as in figure e in the appendix. This northern sector of Riyadh shows the least land use intensity of all.

Table 3: Mean values of Residential & Commercial lot sizes of Riyadh study areas neighborhoods.

Indicators	Riyadh Study Areas (m ²)						
	Deerah	Sector1*	Sector2	Sector3	Sector4	Sector5	Sector6
Residential Lot Size	248.88	676.88	791.22	741.01	742.46	724.54	644.68
Commercial Lot Size	1554.36	1480.04	1582.04	1406.34	917.39	1493.48	2512.94

Sector 1* refers to the whole sector 1 excluding the traditional core area (Deerah).

The same pattern is corroborated when looking at the average commercial lot sizes. The data indicate that Riyadh urban core reveals an average size of only 1554.36 m². But the distribution reveals the existence of a considerable number of small shops of sizes not exceeding 500 m² (see figure b in the appendix). The distributions of commercial lot sizes in the remaining

neighborhoods in the other sectors indicate much larger lot sizes ranging from 1480.04 to 2512.90 m² (See figures b, d, f, h, j, l, and n in the appendix).

5.3 Land Use Mix

Land use mix as indicated by the diversity of uses within a neighborhood is another descriptor of land use intensity. The contention is that the more diversified the uses the more walkable the neighborhood is. Homogeneous neighborhoods would be less pedestrian friendly as they lack such mix of uses to encourage residents to roam about. To measure land use diversity the proportion of lots for other uses than residential within neighborhoods were computed. The higher the proportion the higher the neighborhood land use intensity is. Table 3 below represents the number and proportion of lots for each use in all six sectors of Riyadh. It shows clearly that the *Deerah* neighborhood uses are much more diversified than in any other neighborhood in the city. Neighborhoods of the traditional core or *Deerah* tend to be nearly fully

developed as indicated by the proportion of unbuilt parcels of only 8% whereas, the remaining areas or sectors reveal proportions ranging from 42 to 88% of unbuilt lots. The mere fact of having such a high proportion of unbuilt parcels would adversely affect land use intensity and constitute a major deterrent to walkability. When considering the percentage of developed areas, the results indicate that the older neighborhoods of the inner city (*Deerah*) are nearly fully developed (88.38%). Whereas the Northern Riyadh is the least developed area (42.68%) (Table 5). When looking at the proportion of commercial uses, both the *Deerah* and Southern Riyadh (Sector 4) neighborhoods were singled out as having the highest proportion with about 4 % and 5% respectively.

Table 4: Proportions of land uses in different study areas of the city.

Use	Deerah	Sector1*	Sector 2	Sector 3	Sector 4	Sector 5	Sector 6
Residential	43995 (85%)	53598 (48%)	5543 (7%)	54191 (47%)	28501 (29%)	48527 (36%)	2937 (32%)
Commercial	1937 (4%)	2702 (2%)	200 (0.03%)	2715 (2%)	4841 (5%)	1250 (1%)	134 (1%)
gardens & Parks	57	92	13	94	97	33	5
Governmental	128	66	10	267	62	94	45
health	54	80	13	82	37	53	10
Industrial	25	31	6	31	1216	35	3
Farming	20	178	64	186	238	183	121
Educational	186	525	59	540	282	391	29
Recreational	108	3739	957	3753	2596	2298	758
Warehousing	477	364	144	485	2979	134	56
Mosques	430	646	101	655	455	618	79
Services	258	531	82	541	557	232	52
Cemeteries	28	5	0	5	7	1	4
Unbuilt Parcels	4001 (8%)	47107 (42%)	65171 (88)	47760 (42%)	53711 (55%)	81252 (60%)	4747 (52%)
Unknown Uses	301	2908	1592	2909	1656	1197	192
Grand Total	52005	112572	73955	114214	97235	136298	9172

Sector 1* refers to the whole sector 1 excluding the traditional core area (*Deerah*).

When Looking at the distribution of land uses in different neighborhoods, the data reveal that neighborhoods in the traditional urban core area of Riyadh show a higher proportion of residential and commercial uses than any other area of the city. When

considering the numbers of lots, the figures indicate that the city core area accounts for about 85% of residential lots and 4% of commercial lots. Sector 1, the second in order holds only 48% and 2% for residential and commercial lots respectively (Table 4).

In terms of areas, the traditional core (*Deerah*) shows about 27.2% of residential use areas against only 23.7% for sector1* adjacent to the core area. Sector 2 in the Northern part of Riyadh shows the least proportion of both residential and commercial uses with 2.1% and 0.3% respectively (Table 5). Higher proportions of residential uses in a neighborhood are a proxy for higher intensity and more walkability as

long as there are enough amenities, particularly commercial services, in the area. This is precisely the case for the city core where such commercial uses occupy about 8.8%. On the other hand, the car is king in neighborhoods where such proportions of uses are relatively low as is the case for sector 2 where commercial activities account for only 0.3% (Table 5).

Table 5: Proportions of residential and commercial uses and development rate in different sectors of the city.

	Residential	Commercial	Total Area	% Residential	% Commercial	% Development
Deerah	9016055	1920082	33089544	27.2	5.8	88.38
Sector1*	58354955	8176095	245999237	23.7	3.3	80.2
north	9193106	1535119	441248103	2.1	0.3	42.68
east	42692914	6386242	415977548	10.3	1.5	63.29
south	22582351	7357237	473719156	4.8	1.6	45.81
west	27883869	1996577	438080696	6.4	0.5	54.47
Der'yiah	671502	48840	11202525	6.0	0.4	48

Sector 1* refers to the whole sector 1 excluding the traditional core area (*Deerah*).

The data presented in Table 4 highlights the relative distribution of various land-uses within the different study areas. Overall, the traditional core neighborhood area (known locally as *Deerah*) has a significantly higher land use mix than any other sector of Riyadh. The area contains a broader range of activities, including industrial, recreational, commercial, institutional, and residential. This is mainly attributed to the fact that it is located at the heart of the downtown commercial district. The other sectors of the city however, being of relatively recent development and many of their neighborhoods on the fringe of the city, makes them incomplete residential developments lacking the necessary full range of accompanying services and amenities.

that takes into consideration these various land-uses. For this purpose, a Land-Use Mix Index (LUMI) was established. It takes into account all land use parcels excluding vacant lands. The Land-Use Mix Index (LUMI) is the sum of all land uses divided by the total street length in a neighborhood. As the variety of land-uses increases so does the land-use mix index. That is the higher the LUMI value, the more assorted the distribution of land uses. A high index is therefore, a proxy for land use intensity and for neighborhood attractiveness to pedestrians and walkability. Higher proportion of vacant lands however, reduces walkability as it lowers the number of destinations per unit area. The results indicate that the LUMI is significantly higher at the traditional core (63.75) compared to other areas in the city (Table 6).

For a better account of the assortment of land-use types in any area, it is helpful to use a single measure

Table 6: The Land-Use Mix Index (LUMI) for different study areas in Riyadh

Areas	Deerah	Sector1*	Sector2	Sector3	Sector4	Sector5	Sector6
LUMI	54.74	16.13	3.11	15.09	10.73	12.94	8.54

Sector 1* refers to the whole sector 1 excluding the traditional core area.

The data presented in Table 7 below show that a person's share in residential uses is the lowest in the urban core area with only 32.91 m² per person. This

share increases by about 392.4% for the next area which is sector1* (162.06 m²/person). It rises sharply once again for the remaining sectors 2 through 6

(4242.25 to 705.65 m²/person respectively). This suggests that Riyadh citizens are likely to use excessive residential space if they happen to live in a neighborhood at the outskirts of the city than in the traditional area at the inner city.

Another way of capturing the sprawling characteristics of neighborhood forms is to examine the share of the automobile in terms of road space. Here again, a sizable proportion of the neighborhood area is used for roads. The data show that the share of the car in the core area for example, as measured by road space per

car, is about 139.89 m². This share jumps to a staggering amount of (558.02 m² per car) in sector1* just next to it. It also goes crescendo for the remaining sectors as it amounts up to 995.96 m² per car for sector 3 to hit finally the highest point at sector 2 with 6112.30 m² per car, which is about 44 times what it was in the urban core area (Table 6). The explanation for this lies in the fact that the Riyadh municipality has developed the road network in many peripheral planned neighborhoods in sectors 2 through 6 but the residential units have yet to be built up (figure 4).

Figure 4: A Google earth view that is very common at the outskirts of Riyadh neighborhoods where public services are being laid out but the private dwellings have yet to be built up (the view above from Qurtubah (left) and Al-Janadriyah (right) neighborhood).

The larger share of the car in terms of road space indicates that the neighborhood form tends to be “pedestrian unfriendly” as it privileges more automobile use. In the old city however, the car share

is about the fourth of what it gets in the neighboring Sector1* (139.89 m² vs. 558.02 m²). The city core neighborhood form is therefore, a much more pedestrian friendly environment.

Table 7: Average shares of residential area per person and road area per car

Indicators	Riyadh Study Areas						
	Deerah	Sector1*	Sector2	Sector3	Sector4	Sector5	Sector6
Land Use area per Person (m2/Pers)	32.91	162.06	4242.25	340.23	748.33	457.82	705.65
Road area per Car (m2/Car)	139.89	558.02	6112.30	995.96	1776.11	1668.49	1674.75

Sector 1* refers to the whole sector 1 excluding the traditional core area.

5.4 Street network connectivity measures

Street network connectivity is another important descriptor of neighborhood form. The contention is that new urbanist neighborhood forms would show greater connectivity than sprawling neighborhood forms. Two measures of connectivity are used, internal and external connectivity. Internal connectivity

describes transportation route options within a neighborhood. It is measured by the centerline length of local or minor streets by the neighborhood area. External connectivity on the other hand, depicts route options between neighborhoods and is measured by centerline length of main streets per unit area. Both

types of connectivity portray the overall street network connectivity.

Table 8: Centerline street length per hectare in different study areas of Riyadh

Riyadh Areas	Interconnectedness: Street Network Density Measures					
	Main Street Length (m)	Minor Street Length (m)	Total Street Length (m)	Internal Connectivity (m /ha)	External Connectivity (m /ha)	Overall Connectivity (m /ha)
Deerah	78643.17	798319.1	876962.27	258.61	25.48	284.09
Sector1*	363194.92	3695014.75	4058209.67	134.23	13.19	147.42
Sector2	155723.39	2672671.65	2828395.04	35.88	2.09	37.97
Sector3	185281.77	4219029.21	4404310.98	36.06	1.58	37.64
Sector4	226243.52	3831743.58	4057987.1	42.07	2.48	44.55
Sector5	155126.48	4098198.85	4253325.33	56.39	2.13	58.52
Sector6	50065.48	467784.2	517849.68	3	0.32	3.32

Sector 1* refers to the whole sector 1 excluding the traditional core area.

The results presented in Table 8 indicate that the *Deerah* area shows greater internal and external connectivity as measured by road network intensity (258.61 m/ha for internal connectivity and 25.48 m/ha for external connectivity). Sector 6, the newly annexed area to Riyadh city shows by far the lowest overall street connectivity measures of all (3.32 m/ha). As a new area, the street network (both minor and major roads) has yet to be developed. The external connectivity for the remaining sectors (sectors 2 through 5) is more or less the same. This can be explained by the fact that the legal responsibility of planning and developing the city's major roads rests on the shoulders of only one institutional body, which is the Arriyadh Development Authority (ADA). Sector 1 however, tends to have greater overall connectivity (both internal and external) as all major roads converge to this area because of its central location. As a result, this central sector exhibits many major roads and higher center line length per unit area (13.19 m/ha for external connectivity) as shown in Table 8.

As far as the internal connectivity is concerned, the first sector shows a greater connectivity (134.23 m/ha) due to its central position and its relatively higher level of development which amounts up to over 80%. Sector

2 shows the least level of connectivity (37.97m/ha) because of its lower development rate (42.68%) coupled with its land subdivision development style which consists of larger lots to cater for the demands of its affluent social status residents. The lesser connectivity for neighborhoods outside the *Deerah* area is an indication that they tend to adopt a more sprawl-oriented planning.

Street network connectivity at the neighborhood level depends also to a large extent on block attributes. The following section sets up to examine block size and block perimeter and their impact on neighborhood form.

5.5 Block size and block perimeter measures

Block size and block perimeter are good indicators of either smart growth or sprawling neighborhood forms. Smart growth neighborhood forms tend to have blocks with smaller size and shorter perimeter. Sprawling neighborhoods on the other hand would have longer and bigger blocks. The data presented in Table 9 below seem to confirm this assertion. The *Deerah* neighborhoods tend to have higher block density (1.72 blocks/ha) with a mean size of about 4001.09 m² and a perimeter of 245.12 m in average. More recent neighborhoods in sector 2 tend to have far larger block

size (mean= 39735.61 m²). The *Der'yiah* or sector 6 has the largest block size since much of its land

remains still undeveloped with large tracts waiting to be subdivided.

Table 9: Interconnectedness: Block Density Measures

Riyadh Study Areas	Interconnectedness: Block Density Measures		
	Average Block Area (m ²)	Average Block Perimeter (m)	Block Density/ha
Deerah	4001.09	245.12	1.72
Sector1*	10849.78	369	0.68
Sector2	51528.28	547	0.12
Sector3	66349.12	542	0.14
Sector4	61441.16	640	0.14
Sector5	39735.61	584	0.21
Sector6	808668.51	2889	0.01

Sector 1* refers to the whole sector 1 excluding the traditional core area.

Street connectivity and block attributes are also a proxy for pedestrian accessibility. The argument is that interconnected streets beget smaller block sizes and hence pedestrian friendly neighborhood forms. Lesser street connectivity on the other hand would lead to larger blocks thus producing sprawling neighborhood forms and therefore less walkable environments. The following paragraphs will focus upon this issue of accessibility.

5.6 Measures of Accessibility

The five indicators to measure pedestrian accessibility are commercial establishments, primary governmental schools, local mosques, neighborhood parks and primary health care establishments. The measurement variables consist of using a threshold of 5 minutes (about half kilometer distance) as the “cost” field to determine the number of households covered by the amenity service area. For neighborhood mosques however, the catchment area was set up at a threshold of 275 meters radius as required by the municipality subdivision code. The argument is the higher the number of households serviced by these amenities the greater the pedestrian accessibility in a neighborhood.

The data provided in Table 10 below indicates that the traditional core area (*Deerah*) has the highest percentage of households within the thresholds set for

walking distance service areas. Well over ninety percent of households in this core area enjoy full amenity coverage of primary educational services (94.7%), local neighborhood mosques (99.67%) and commercial establishments such as grocery stores, eating places, and other day-to-day businesses (93.6%).

Such proportion decreases sharply when looking at service area coverage for households living in the remaining sectors. Only 87.68% of households in the first sector tend to be within a walking distance from primary schools. With regard to commercial establishments, the majority of households cannot get to this amenity within 5 minutes walk, as only a proportion of 48.40% of them are within the catchment area of these commercial services.

When examining primary health care and neighborhood parks service area coverage, the data show that even households living in the core area of Riyadh tend to be at a disadvantage as only a tiny percentage (36.48% and 53.69%) of households are within the 5 minutes walk threshold of primary health care establishments and local neighborhood parks respectively. Such percentages are much lower for households in the remaining sectors of Riyadh. The data for Sector 2 for example, indicate only some elfin percentages of 0.46% and 18.65% of households covered by these health and recreational services.

Table 10: Percentage of households within walking distance of the five amenities.

Amenity	Deerah	Sector1*	Sector2	Sector3	Sector4	Sector5	Sector6
Primary educational establishments	94.7%	87.68%	28.99%	81.20%	51.36%	86.87%	73.66%
Commercial Services	93.6%	48.40%	3.97%	37.23%	24.23%	48.02%	71.31%
Places of Worship	99.67%	93.61%	76.18%	94.74%	67.32%	96.21%	96.63%
Primary Health care	36.48%	21.02%	0.46%	6.03%	6.10%	0.83%	20.06%
Neighborhood Parks	53.69%	52.85%	18.65%	23.55%	16.25%	11.38%	39.06%

Sector 1* refers to the whole sector 1 excluding the traditional core area.

Overall, for all of the five amenities examined, the city core holds a higher percentage of households within walking distance. It is therefore clear that neighborhood subdivision patterns of the traditional core area present far greater pedestrian accessibility than the more recent neighborhoods with modern conventional design patterns scattered all over Riyadh City.

5.7 Concluding Remarks

This research paper has been undertaken in an attempt to characterize urban neighborhood forms and the relevant characteristics to reveal trends at the micro level using neighborhood morphological elements.

A number of quantifiable spatial attributes, such as density, land use mix and street network connectivity were assessed to quantify patterns of neighborhood form. A comparative characterization of recent Riyadh neighborhoods relative to traditional central core neighborhoods was used. For all the measures calculated, the inner city (*Deerah*) neighborhood forms tend to perform far better than any other neighborhood form in the city in terms of walkability, social interaction and neighboring.

The traditional city core embraces a set of urban regulations quite different from the modern zoning codes adopted by the more recent conventional suburban developments (CSD) of Riyadh neighborhoods. Conventional suburban developments (CSD) zoning regulations insist more on single land uses (mainly residential), building setbacks and street right-of-ways for car movement. By so doing, they hinder walkability, mixing of uses and result in relatively homogeneous neighborhoods. One may safely infer that such poor scores along the measured

neighborhood form attributes might be a response to these use-based zoning subdivision regulations and design codes. The traditional principles of neighborhood design adopted mainly for inner city neighborhoods are much in line with the precepts of New Urbanism and its traditional-oriented building standards. This explains to a large extent the discrepancies revealed between the inner city and outer core neighborhoods.

The results indicate a clear relationship between urban neighborhood form characteristics and walkability. That is, neighborhood forms that tend to encourage walking are those that have mixed-uses, neighborhood compactness, interconnected streets and higher residential densities. Land use planners should therefore seek denser, and more diverse neighborhood forms as their goal for future developments in Riyadh. The above findings are policy-relevant in the sense that policymakers can use to inform zoning and subdivision regulations to control density, street network connectivity, land use diversity and intensity; as well as select the location of schools and businesses, and all other services and amenities.

Since Riyadh contains large tracts of undeveloped land either within developed areas or at its vicinity, this presents an opportunity for city planners to curb the sprawling tendency of development in favor for more "New Urbanist" approaches to neighborhood form planning and design. Today's sprawl could therefore, turn into compact and sustainable development in later years as the pace of urban extension drives developers to fill-in previously undeveloped sites.

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APPENDIX

Note: In the frequency distributions below, the X axis indicate the values of the land parcel areas, whereas the Y axis is the frequency or number of occurrences of these values.

Figure a: Residential Parcels
Frequency distributions of City core residential and commercial parcels

Figure b: Commercial Parcels

Figure c: Residential Parcels
Frequency distributions of Sector1* residential and commercial parcels

Figure d: Commercial Parcels

Figure e: Residential Parcels
Frequency distributions of Sector2 residential and commercial parcels

Figure f: Commercial Parcels

Figure g: Residential Parcels
Frequency distributions of Sector3 residential and commercial parcels

Figure h: Commercial Parcels

Figure i: Residential Parcels
Frequency distributions of Sector4 residential and commercial parcels

Figure j: Commercial Parcels

Figure k: Residential Parcels
Frequency distributions of Sector5 residential and commercial parcels

Figure l: Commercial Parcels

Figure m: Residential Parcels
Frequency distributions of Sector6 (Der'yah) residential and commercial parcels

Figure n: Commercial Parcels